

Shining a Light on Cellulose: From Waste to Worth

Contact:

Pádraig McDonagh,
Department of Life & Physical
Sciences,
Atlantic Technological University
(ATU) Donegal

Email: Padraig.mcdonagh@atu.ie

Further Reading: McDonagh, P., Shanks, K., Ralphs, K., Skillen, N. & McCrudden, D. (2026). From commercial photocatalysts to concentrated solar systems: mechanistic elucidation of cellulose depolymerisation. *Journal of Physics: Energy* 8 (2)
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Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Biomass is an abundant renewable carbon source, yet it remains under-exploited due to the energy-intensive and costly nature of traditional conversion. Central to this challenge is cellulose, its primary component. Unlocking its chemical value may be key to decarbonising fuels and chemical manufacturing, but success hinges on mastering the complex depolymerisation process. Photocatalysis offers a sustainable pathway to break down these polymer chains under mild low-carbon conditions. To move from lab concepts to deployable systems, we must prioritise understanding the mechanisms of the depolymerisation process. By combining these mechanistic insights with scalable, solar-driven technologies, we can deliver a tangible impact on the global bioeconomy.

Research Findings

This study utilised di- to tetra-saccharide model systems to identify the mechanism of photocatalytic depolymerisation of cellulose using commercial catalysts. Findings revealed that Zinc Oxide (ZnO) provided significantly higher glucose selectivity; however, efficiency declined as chain length increased. This represents a critical hurdle for real-world feedstocks, necessitating rigorous benchmarking of photocatalysts to ensure commercial viability. By identifying the pivotal role of photogenerated holes and reactive oxygen species, this work determined the depolymerisation pathway and associated oxidation mechanisms. Moreover, the study demonstrated that concentrated solar irradiation effectively activated ZnO, overcoming the low proportion of UV light in the solar spectrum.

Policy Implications

Current policy demonstrates growing recognition of the bioeconomy yet support for emerging conversion technologies such as photocatalysis is still developing. The findings on the efficiency hurdles suggest that prioritising standardised benchmarking is essential to inform investment and guide technological development. Such benchmarking must be integrated with system-level considerations, including reactor design and scale-up, to ensure future deployment. Increased support for pilot-scale demonstration and integrated solar-driven systems is required to validate performance under practical conditions. Ultimately, a balanced policy approach supporting rigorous benchmarking and system integration is vital for advancing solar-driven biomass conversion toward commercial deployment.

Industry Recommendations

To bridge the gap between lab-scale innovation and commercial application, industry requires robust policy roadmaps. Specifically, technologies like photocatalysis need clear pathways through Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) to ensure market integration. Rather than focusing solely on catalyst design, attention should be given to deployable, system-level solutions using commercially available materials. Progress requires coordinated advances in reactor engineering, light management, and integration with existing solar and biorefinery infrastructure. In parallel, improved utilisation of the full solar spectrum, including strategies to redirect underused light into complementary applications, will enhance overall efficiency and economic feasibility, supporting the low-carbon transition.

